

DIRECTIONS FOR MODERNIZING THE SELF-EVALUATION AND CONTINUOUS EVALUATION OF THE STUDENT'S RESULTS. FROM COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY TO ICT SYSTEMS

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Abstract

It requires major changes in the processes of self-assessment and continuous assessment of pupils' achievement to meet contemporary society's challenges.

In this research study, we presented the current approach of the evaluative issue in its transition from informatics technology to evaluative information systems and technology communication (ITC).

When conducting the research, we studied teachers' references on the role of the ITC systems in pupils' self-assessment and the contribution of the automated continuous assessment to improving pupils' learning activity.

The general hypothesis of the research project aimed to demonstrate that if secondary school teachers are aware of the role of the self-assessment ICT systems and of continuous digital assessment, then there is obtained their adherence to implementing and developing such systems of assessment.

To study the relationship between research variables we applied a questionnaire, with teachers as the target group.

The conducted study has positively impacted the respondent teachers, who adhered to the proposed idea, being confident in the role of transition from the self-assessment of informatics refurbishment and continuous assessment of pupils' achievement in implementing the ITC systems in the educational assessment.

Keywords: *self-assessment, continuous assessment, informatics refurbishment, ITC systems of assessment.*

One of the major problems facing educational research today is Internet-based platforms. They are designed to improve the learning activity of the students generating new challenges for which we must identify solutions. Our education system must look for

new solutions for the development of e-learning systems through which we can track students' progress and automatically evaluate their practical activities. Thus, we intend to study the evaluative problem in its transition from the traditional practice based on the development of students' abilities of technological operation to modern evaluative systems of information and technological communication (ICT). Making a foray into the issue of evaluation, Jean Vogler concludes quite trenchantly: its universe is neither coherent, nor homogeneous, nor consensual:

"It is not homogeneous and coherent because of the various currents that cross it. Two assessment systems coexist today. The first is traditional, secular, and therefore strongly anchored in the mentality of its actors. In addition to this, and somewhat against it, a different kind of assessment developed towards the end of the '60s, which we might call modern" (Vogler, 2000).

In addition, current theories on education strongly promote the idea that modern assessment must be an integral part of the learning process, to be associated with it.

From the perspective of the curricular and systemic approach of the educational process, it is unanimously accepted the idea, according to which, the evaluation is an integral part of a whole, it should not be treated in isolation, but in close correlation with the other activities through which the educational process is carried out, with teaching and learning.

On the other hand, evaluation methods, techniques, and tools cannot be dissociated from the other variables of evaluation: the object of evaluation (which is evaluated), educational criteria/objectives, evaluative strategies, etc. All these are like the elements of a puzzle: to understand its meaning, you have to order its parts.

Going on the same coordinates of the analysis of the modernization of the evaluation in the current stage, Constantin Cucos also insists on the distance and the fundamental distinction of this process from the classical control of knowledge or traditional measurement, with values of objectivity and conception of the evaluation as a way of improvement, which implies a global strategy of formation:

"In the modern sense, the evaluation should not be understood as an over-added or superimposed stage to the learning process, but constitutes an act integrated to the pedagogical activity." (Cucos, 2008).

Evaluation is of less and less interest in terms of measurements and results and more and more in terms of its processuality.

"School evaluation is increasingly conceived as an integrated part of the learning process and its milestone" (Abernot, 1996, p.5). In recent decades pedagogy has paid great attention to the study of the concept of "formative" assessment, which assigns assessment an important role in the formation of the student, analyzing the progress of his competencies.

Modern evaluation marks the evolution from the role of controlling the acquired knowledge to that of evaluating the learning outcomes and the processes involved, basic components of the structure of the teaching activity.

Ioan Cerghit states that evaluation is a "science of value" (p.287), which refers to a system of value judgments. Thus, " education declares its priorities for a certain value system, justifies its options and preferences about certain values translated into objectives. These values must be appropriated and internalized by the student, to integrate them into his structures of knowledge and feeling, into his conduct."

(Cerghit, p.288, în Potolea, D.; Manolescu, M., 2005).

Evaluation, along with teaching and learning, should be seen as a single unit to which we relate: "We need to talk about evaluation in terms of processes. Instead of the term devoted to evaluation, we need to talk about 'evaluative activity', 'evaluation in action, ongoing.'" (Manolescu, 2004).

In this sense, evaluation becomes an approach focused on the active involvement of the student in learning, on his cognitive processes, and on the regulation and self-regulation of knowledge, disregarding his role as a simple tool used in measuring and controlling the didactic process. But processing means processing. The result of information processing is the formation of capacities and competencies.

The transformation of competence into the finality of the educational process and an "object of evaluation" is the result of shifting the emphasis from the products of learning to the processes involved in the learning activity. The object of the evaluation can be defined as the educational reality materialized in the process and product of learning, submitted to the evaluator's attention, to be measured and appreciated. Through evaluation, judgments are made regarding the value of the process and the product of learning carried out by the student.

Self-assessment – is the assessment carried out by the student on what he has achieved and/or on his behavior. It helps students to develop their capacities of self-knowledge and to value both their knowledge and their attitudes and behaviors.

"Self-evaluation is possible and necessary because it serves the knowledge (perception) of self (self-knowledge) and the development of self-awareness (self-consciousness), essential aspects that will give the possibility, in time, to everyone to discover the meaning of their value, a prerequisite necessary for any overcoming; a willingness seen in the perspective of lifelong learning, which involves engaging the individual not only in the process of his training but also in the action of evaluating his training to become capable of self-improvement." (Cerghit, 2005, p. 312).

Important is the entire situational context that acts on the student's formation. The assessment must be student-centered and implicitly, and the learning process must be adapted to the student's training needs. If we analyze digital learning methods and techniques, assessment as a process becomes an important and basic tool in the learning process (Carswell et al., 2000; Morgan et al., 2002; Schrum et al., 2007).

By choosing the forms of assessment, it is the school that determines the student's learning by adapting the contents of the student's learning rhythm. The online interaction between the school and the students determines the increase in the efficiency of the evaluation process to achieve the level of the previous objectives. (Robles-Gómez et al., 2011; Agudo et al., 2011).

Through an automated evaluation system, teachers can make a more detailed record of the school progress of each student and as many students as possible. In this way, the practical activities of the students are evaluated and their shortcomings are identified.

This evaluation system supports teachers by specifying the weaknesses in the learning process in the reports they generate. Evaluative practices cannot be possible in a traditional evaluation system that is based on questionnaires, closed or open-answer questions, and ignores practical activities.

The information provided by the assessment information systems can be focused on adapting the content and resources to the individual particularities of the students. The students can thus obtain feedback on the cross-cutting activities carried out, which is not present in the traditional assessment that is based on the interpretation of the reports of each field of activity. The integration of the computer into the school curriculum is a complex process in continuous modernization from the perception of the computer as a material resource that improves the work of the teacher and students to the integration of the computer in learning and evaluation for the formation and development of competencies.

Current learning platforms are based on the ratio of students to content. They have the role of centralizing learning, relying on the content, and promoting evaluation methods centered on theoretical content. In this case, the students can be immediately checked their level of knowledge through multiple-choice items or exercises of the association of concepts (Douce et al., 2005)

Therefore, the successful use of information technologies requires new skills that cannot be achieved in a traditional education environment. It requires interaction, access, and uses that are not conditioned by time and space.

An educational program is needed to execute the continuous evaluation of the process of evaluating progress made by the student and to indicate what road he must take to reach the threshold of efficiency.

In this respect, useful is the advanced systems for managing self-evaluation and continuous evaluation, which are understood as a set of web services. These service-oriented applications can be considered the latest discoveries in technological computerization and communication platforms.

Conclusions

Summarizing, we can specify the following points.

The paper presents several personal contributions:

- Addressing the dimensions and roles of ICT systems for evaluating student outcomes to manage self-evaluation and continuous evaluation of student's progress;
- Bringing into a discussion a concept less studied in the specialized literature, of informatization and technological communication of the activities of self-evaluation and continuous evaluation, determining the criteria of the evolution of the ICT evaluation systems.

The continuous evaluation and self-evaluation of students' results need the development of complex systems involving various information technologies (configuration files, software bases, or implementation units), as well as the speed of the software or the evolution of operating systems. Therefore, it is found to be of utmost importance to implement a generic solution that develops transversal competencies for students.

Bibliografie:

ABERNOT, Y. (1998). *Les méthodes d'évaluation scolaire. Nouvelle édition.* Paris: DUNOD

CARSWELL, L., THOMAS, P., PETRE, M., PRICE, B., & RICHARDS, M. (2000). Distance education via the Internet: The student experience. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 31(1), 29–46

CUCOȘ, C. (2008). Teoria și metodologia evaluării. București: Editura Polirom

DOUCE, C., LIVINGSTONE, D., & ORWELL, J. (2005). Automatic test-based assessment of programming: A review. *Journal on Educational Resources in Computing*, 5(3), 1–13.

MANOLESCU, M. (2004). *Activitatea evaluativă între cogniție și metacogniție*. București: Editura Meteor

MORGAN, CH. & O'REILLY. (2002). *Assessing Open and Distance Learners*. London, United Kingdom: Kogan

POTOLEA, D., MANOLESCU, M. (2005). Teoria și practica evaluării-curs universitar. În *Proiectul pentru Învățământ Rural*. București. Preluat pe 24.02.2012 de pe <http://www.scribd.com/doc/148035655/Teoria-Si-Practica-Evaluarii>.

ROBLES-GÓMEZ, A., TOBARRA, L., ROS, S., HERNÁNDEZ, R., CAMINERO, A. C., PASTOR, R., & CASTRO, M. (2011, April). Proposal of an Auto-Evaluation Framework for the Learning of Network Services. In A. Y. Al-Zoubi et al. (Eds.), *Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON), 2011 IEEE* (pp. 392–396). Amman, Jordan: IEEE Education Society.

SCHRUM, L., BURBANK, M. D., & CAPPS, R. (2007). Preparing future teachers for diverse schools in an online learning community: Perceptions and practice. *Internet & Higher Education*, 10(3), 204–211

VOGLER, J. (2000). *Evaluarea în învățământul preuniversitar*. Iași: Editura Polirom